

Enhancing Phenotype Libraries with Phenoflow

“ We hope that by making our research objects available via repositories like Zenodo, we will encourage others to explore the reproducibility of our methods, thus ultimately contributing to our collective understanding of the areas under study. ”

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Computable Phenotypes: [Phenoflow implementation units](#)

Website: <https://kclhi.org/phenoflow/>

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Related publication: Chapman, M., Rasmussen, L., Pacheco, J., & Curcin, V. (2023). Using Version Control Systems to Support High-Quality Phenotype Definitions. In *American Medical Informatics Association (AMIA) Informatics Summit*

Background

In the field of biomedical informatics, computable phenotypes - algorithmic definitions of clinical conditions derived from Electronic Health Records - play a pivotal role in identifying patient cohorts and enabling reproducible research. These phenotypes are commonly housed in phenotype libraries, which act as centralized repositories for researchers. However, many existing libraries are limited in functionality, often serving as static stores without adequate support for data sharing, version control, or reuse.

To overcome these limitations, the Phenoflow platform - a microservice-based architecture that supports the authoring, sharing, and execution of computable phenotypes - uses GitHub to enable robust version control and historical tracking. This promotes transparency, reproducibility, and formal attribution, ensuring that phenotype definitions can evolve while maintaining traceability and integrity.

The image shows a composite of two screenshots. The top screenshot is the abstract of a paper titled "Using Version Control to Support High-Quality Phenotype Definitions" by Chapman, Martin¹; Rasmussen, Luke²; Pacheco, Jennifer²; Curcin, Vasa¹. It features four diagrams illustrating Phenoflow's capabilities: 1. Versioning (by default): Shows two boxes for 'phenoflow' with different 'long_covid_assessment' values, with a note that cross-repository diffs allow comparing versions for the same disease. 2. Branching: Shows two 'phenoflow' boxes connected by a branching structure, with a note that it supports multiple (data source) implementations. 3. Submodules: Shows a 'phenoflow' box containing submodules for 'Long-covid.git', 'Long-covid-post-hospitalization.git', and 'Long-covid-community-care.git', with a note to connect nested definitions. 4. Visualisations: Shows a 'phenoflow' box connected to a 'COMMON WORKFLOW LANGUAGE' box, with a note to retain an abstract layer. The bottom screenshot shows the GitHub repository for 'kclhi / phenoflow', displaying the README, MIT license, and repository statistics like 17 branches and 0 tags.

Evolution of Data Sharing

The landscape of phenotype data sharing has evolved significantly in recent years. Increasingly, research objects such as code, posters, and datasets are being cited. While this trend marks meaningful progress, the widespread adoption of such practices is still emerging. As part of this evolution, a collection of Phenoflow-related records is available on Zenodo, including code repositories and computable phenotype definitions. These records contribute to a more transparent and reusable research ecosystem by providing persistent identifiers and open access to key research artifacts.

Challenges and Solutions

As Phenoflow evolved into a platform for sharing computable phenotypes, key needs emerged:

- Ability to host diverse research outputs
- Ensure persistent citation through DOI assignment
- Support transparency and reuse

Zenodo addressed these needs by:

- Supporting multiple file types
- Assigning DOIs
- Integrating with GitHub to automate the publication of version-controlled materials—streamlining the entire data sharing lifecycle

Impact of Data Sharing

By leveraging Zenodo to share research materials and integrating existing technologies to achieve specific research goals, Phenoflow delivers a comprehensive and reproducible representation of its work. This approach not only enhances transparency but also fosters new collaborations and helps existing partners gain a deeper understanding of the project's scope and impact. In doing so, Phenoflow's strategy offers a model for other disciplines seeking to enhance the reproducibility and impact of their research.

Looking Forward

Generalist repositories will hopefully become increasingly integrated into the research publishing process, with journals and conferences encouraging or automating the deposit of research objects. As adoption grows across academia and industry, we expect a parallel rise in supporting infrastructure and enhanced repository features, further embedding these platforms into the fabric of open, reproducible science.

Accelerating Research Sharing and Reuse with Zenodo and GREI

Zenodo and **GREI** work collaboratively to support researchers in sharing, preserving, and reusing data across disciplines.

Zenodo is an open-access repository developed by **CERN** through the **OpenAIRE program**. For over a decade, it has enabled researchers to share, preserve, and cite diverse research outputs. Powered by **InvenioRDM**, Zenodo offers a flexible, open-source foundation that supports modern research workflows and data management best practices. **InvenioRDM** is the engine and community behind Zenodo. Learn more and connect with the InvenioRDM open source community!

The **Generalist Repository Ecosystem Initiative (GREI)** is a collaborative effort funded by the NIH Office of Data Science Strategy to enhance access to and reuse of research data. GREI supports a network of generalist repositories like Zenodo to promote open science, data sharing, and reproducibility across disciplines.

GREI: Real-World Impact

- Funded by the **NIH Office of Data Science Strategy 10T2DB000013**
- Promotes **transparent, reproducible, and scalable** research

Learn more:

- 🖥️ Try it out! <https://inveniordm.web.cern.ch>
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Generalist Repository Ecosystem Initiative (GREI) Community <https://zenodo.org/communities/grei/>

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